

PREDICTING FRAUDS IN INSURANCE CLAIMS USING MACHINE LEARNING

¹ P. SAI BABU PG STUDENT IN DEPT OF CSE IN SREE VAHINI INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, TIRUVURU, NTR DISTRICT, 521235, A.P.

² P. VEERASWAMI M. TECH, ASSISTANT PROFESSOR IN DEPT OF CSE IN SREE VAHINI INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, TIRUVURU, NTR DISTRICT, 521235, A.P.

ABSTRACT: Patients depend on health insurance provided by the government systems, private systems, or both to utilize the high-priced healthcare expenses. This dependency on health insurance draws some healthcare service providers to commit insurance frauds. Although the number of such service providers is small, it is reported that the insurance providers lose billions of dollars every year due to frauds. In this paper, I formulate the fraud detection problem over a minimal, definitive claim data consisting of medical diagnosis and procedure codes. I present a solution to the fraudulent claim detection problem using a novel representation learning approach, which translates diagnosis and procedure codes into Mixtures of Clinical Codes (MCC). I also investigate extensions of MCC using Long Short Term Memory networks and Robust Principal Component Analysis. My experimental results demonstrate promising outcomes in identifying fraudulent records.

INTRODUCTION

DATA analytics has progressively become crucial to almost any economic development area. Since healthcare is one of the largest financial sectors in the US economy, the massive amount of data, including health records, clinical data, prescriptions, insurance claims, provider information, and patient information “potentially” presents incredible opportunities for data analysts. Health insurance agencies process billions of claims every year and health care expenses is over three trillion dollars in the United States [1]. Figure 1 presents a concise flow of a typical healthcare reconciliation process by using different entities involved. First, the service provider’s office ensures that the patient has adequate coverage through his/her insurance plan or other funds before getting any service. Next, the service provider identifies relevant diagnoses based on the initial examinations performed on the patient. The service provider then runs tests on the patient using one or more medical interventions such as further diagnostics and surgical procedures. These diagnoses and procedures are usually tagged with the patient’s report along with other information such as personal, demographic, and

past/present visit information. At this point, the patient typically pays a copay defined in his/her insurance plan and checks out. Then, the patient's report is sent to a medical coder who abstracts the information and creates a "superbill" containing all information about the provider. Given the economic volume of the healthcare industry, it is natural to observe fraudulent and fabricated claims submitted to insurance companies. The National Health Care Anti- Fraud Association (NHCAA) defines healthcare fraud as "An intentional deception or misrepresentation made by a person, or an entity, with the knowledge that the deception could result in some unauthorized benefit to him or some other entities" [3]. Those fabricated claims bear a very high cost, albeit they constitute a small fraction. According to NHCAA the fraud related financial loss is in the orders of tens of billions of dollars in the United States [3]. Although there are strict policies regarding fraud and abuse control in healthcare industries, studies show that a very small portion of the losses are recovered annually [4]. Typical fraudulent activities committed by dishonest providers in the healthcare domain include the following. _ Making false diagnoses to justify procedures that are not medically necessary. _ Billing for high priced procedures or services instead of the actual procedures, also called "upcoding". _ Fabricating claims for unperformed procedures. _ Performing medically unnecessary procedures to claim insurance payments. _ Billing for each step of a procedure as if it is a separate procedure, also called "unbundling". _ Misrepresenting non-covered treatments as medically necessary to receive insurance payments, especially for cosmetic procedures.

We represent an insurance claim as a Mixture of latent Clinical Concepts (MCC) using probabilistic topic modeling. To the best of our knowledge this is the first work representing insurance claims as mixtures of clinical concepts in a latent space. We assume that every claim is a representation of latent or obvious mixtures of clinical concepts such as pain, mental or infectious diseases. Moreover, each clinical concept is a mixture of clinical codes, i.e., diagnosis and procedure codes. The intuition behind our model comes from the services provided by doctor's offices, clinics, and hospitals. In general, a patient gets services based on specific issues consisting of one or more diagnoses. Next, the service provider performs necessary procedures to treat the patient. Therefore, the diagnoses and procedures in a claim can be represented as a mixture of clinical concepts such as pain, mental, infectious diseases and/or their treatments. Note that, we do not explicitly label or interpret these concepts, as they are often not obvious, complex or require domain knowledge. We extend the MCC model using Long-Short Term Memory networks and Robust Principal Component Analysis.

Our goal in extending MCC is to filter the significant concepts from claims and classify them as fraudulent or non-fraudulent. We extend MCC by using the concept weights of a claim as a sequence representation within a Long-Short Term Memory (LSTM) network. This network allows us to represent the claims as sequences of dependent concepts to be classified by the LSTM. Similarly, we apply Robust Principal Component Analysis (RPCA) to filter significant concept weights by decomposing claims into a low-rank and sparse vector representations. The low-rank matrix ideally captures the noise-free weights.

LITERATURE SURVEY

Title: Predicting frauds in insurance claims using Machine Learning Authors: Md Enamul Haque, Mehmet Engin Tozal Year: 2021 Abstract: The paper proposes a novel approach to detect fraudulent health insurance claims by representing them as mixtures of clinical concepts using a probabilistic topic modeling technique. This method involves translating diagnosis and procedure codes into a latent space, capturing both obvious and subtle indicators of fraud. Experimental results demonstrate that this approach is effective in identifying fraudulent claims in large datasets, offering significant improvements over traditional detection methods. Source: IEEE Transactions on Services Computing (Stanford Profiles) (sci-hub).

Title: Negative Insurance Claim Generation Using Distance Pooling on Positive Diagnosis Procedure Bipartite Graphs Authors: Md Enamul Haque, Mehmet Engin Tozal Year: 2022 Abstract: This research addresses the challenge of generating negative insurance claims, which are crucial for training fraud detection models. The authors introduce a method that pools distances on bipartite graphs formed by diagnosis and procedure codes to generate realistic negative samples. This approach enhances the robustness and accuracy of fraud detection systems by providing a more balanced and representative dataset. Source: ACM Journal of Data and Information Quality (Stanford Profiles).

Title: Predicting Acute Endophthalmitis for Patients with Cataract Surgery Using Hierarchical and Probabilistic Representation of Clinical Codes Authors: Md. Enamul-Haque, S. Pershing, Year: 2022 Abstract: This paper extends the concept of using clinical codes for predictive modelling in healthcare, specifically targeting acute endophthalmitis post-cataract surgery. By employing hierarchical and probabilistic models, the study demonstrates the potential of clinical codes in predicting rare but severe outcomes, which can also be

applied to detect unusual patterns indicative of-fraudulent activities. Source: International Journal of Semantic Computing (Stanford Profiles).

EXISTING SYSTEM

Yang and Hwang developed a fraud detection model using the clinical pathways concept and process-mining framework that can detect frauds in the healthcare domain [13]. The method uses a module that works by discovering structural patterns from input positive and negative clinical instances. The most frequent patterns are extracted from every clinical instance using the module. Next, a feature-selection module is used to create a filtered dataset with labelled features. Finally, an inductive model is built on the feature set for evaluating new claims. Their method uses clustering, association analysis, and principal component analysis. The technique was applied on a real-world data set collected from National Health Insurance (NHI) program in Taiwan. Although the authors constructed different features to generate patterns for both normal and abusive claims, the significance of those features is not discussed. Bayer Stadler et al. [14] presented a predictive model to detect fraud and abuse using manually labelled claims as training data. The method is designed to predict the fraud and abuse score using a probability distribution for new claim invoices. Specifically, the authors proposed a Bayesian network to summarize medical claims' representation patterns using latent variables. In the prediction step, a multinomial variable modelling predicts the probability scores for various fraud events. Additionally, they estimated the model parameters using Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) [15]. Zhang et al. [16] proposed a Medicare fraud detection framework using the concept of anomaly detection [17]. First part of the proposed method consists of a spatial density-based algorithm which is claimed to be more suitable compared to local outlier factors in medical insurance data. The second part of the method uses regression analysis to identify the linear dependencies among different variables. Additionally, the authors mentioned that the method has limited application on new incoming data.

DISADVANTAGES OF EXISTING SYSTEM:

- Making false diagnoses to justify procedures that are not medically necessary. Fabricating claims for unperformed procedures.
- Performing medically unnecessary procedures to claim insurance payments.
- Billing for each step of a procedure as if it is a separate procedure, also called “unbundling”.
- Misrepresenting non-covered treatments as medically necessary to receive insurance payments, especially for cosmetic procedures.

PROPOSED SYSTEM

We extend the MCC model using Long-Short Term Memory networks and Robust Principal Component Analysis. Our goal in extending MCC is to filter the significant concepts from claims and classify them as fraudulent or non-fraudulent. We extend MCC by using the concept weights of a claim as a sequence representation within a Long-Short Term Memory (LSTM) network. This network allows us to represent the claims as sequences of dependent concepts to be classified by the LSTM. Similarly, we apply Robust Principal Component Analysis (RPCA) to filter significant concept weights by decomposing claims into a low-rank and sparse vector representations. The low-rank matrix ideally captures the noise-free weights. Our unique contributions in this study can be summarized as follows. The system formulates the fraudulent claim detection problem over a minimal, definitive claim data consisting of procedure and diagnosis codes. The system introduces clinical concepts over procedure and diagnosis codes as a new representation learning approach. The system extends the mixtures of clinical concepts using LSTM and RPCA for classification.

ADVANTAGES OF PROPOSED SYSTEM: The proposed system uses Support Vector Machine (SVM) for classification with MCC. $\rightarrow$ Multivariate Outlier Detection method is an effective method which is used to detect anomalous provider payments within Medicare claims data.

SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

To conduct studies and analyses of an operational and technological nature, and To promote the exchange and development of methods and tools for operational analysis as applied to defense problems.

INPUT AND OUTPUT DESIGNS LOGICAL DESIGN: The logical design of a system pertains to an abstract representation of the data flows, inputs and outputs of the system. This is often conducted via modeling, using an over-abstract (and sometimes graphical) model of the actual system. In the context of systems design are included. Logical design includes ER Diagrams i.e. Entity Relationship Diagrams.

INPUT DESIGN: The input design is the link between the information system and the user. It comprises the developing specification and procedures for data preparation and those steps are necessary to put transaction data in to a usable form for processing can be achieved by inspecting the computer to read data from a written or printed document or it can occur by having people keying the data directly into the system. The design of input focuses on controlling the amount of input required, controlling the errors, avoiding delay, avoiding extra steps and keeping the process simple.

OUTPUT DESIGN: A quality output is one, which meets the requirements of the end user and presents the information clearly. In any system results of processing are communicated to the users and to other system through outputs. In output design it is determined how the information is to be displaced for immediate need and also the hard copy output. It is the most important and direct source information to the user. Efficient and intelligent output design improves the system's relationship to help user decision-making. a. Designing computer output should proceed in an organized, well thought out manner; the right output must be developed while ensuring that each output element is designed so that people will find the system can use easily and effectively. When analysis design computer output, they should Identify the specific output that is needed to meet the requirements. b. Select methods for presenting information. c. Create document, report, or other formats that contain information produced by the system.

OBJECTIVES: Input Design is the process of converting a user-oriented description of the input into a computer-based system. This design is important to avoid errors in the data input process and show the correct direction to the management for getting correct information from the computerized system. It is achieved by creating user-friendly screens for the data entry to handle large volume of data. The goal of designing input is to make data entry easier and to be free from errors. The data entry screen is designed in such a way that all the data manipulates can be performed. It also provides record viewing facilities. When the data is entered it will check for its validity. Data can be entered with the help of screens. Appropriate messages are provided as when needed so that the user will not be in maize of instant.

OUTPUT RESULTS

Predicting Frauds in Insurance Claims Using Machine Learning

[Home](#) | [Remote User](#) | [Service Provider](#)

Predicting Frauds in Insurance Claims Using Machine Learning
Healthcare, Insurance, Fraud, Mixture Model, Clinical Concepts.

HEALTH INSURANCE

User Name:

Password:

Login

User Login

Healthcare, Insurance, Fraud, Mixture Model, Clinical Concepts.

REGISTER NOW!

REGISTER YOUR DETAILS HERE !!!

Enter Username	<input type="text" value="UserName"/>	Enter Password	<input type="password" value="Password"/>
Enter EMail id	<input type="text" value="Enter Email"/> Admin	Enter Address	<input type="text" value="Enter Address"/>
Enter Gender	<input type="text" value="Select Gender"/> Ashok	Enter Mobile Number	<input type="text" value="Enter Mobile Number"/>
Enter Country Name	<input type="text" value="Enter Country Name"/>	Enter State Name	<input type="text" value="Enter State Name"/>
Enter City Name	<input type="text" value="Enter City Name"/>	<input type="button" value="REGISTER"/>	

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q
1	RID	Sum Insur age	sex	weight	bmi	hereditari	no_of_de	smoker	city	bloodpres	diabetes	regular_e	job_title	claim	Label		
2	3zhptpup	2,00,000	60 male	64	24.3	NoDiseas	1	0	Mumbay	72	0	0	Actor	13112.6	0		
3	z0sfqbfr	4,00,000	49 female	75	22.6	NoDiseas	1	0	Bangalore	78	1	1	Engineer	9567	1		
4	yj2l5bcu	2,00,000	32 female	64	17.8	Epilepsy	2	1	Hydrabad	88	1	1	Academic	32734.2	0		
5	y78y6b25	4,00,000	61 female	53	36.4	NoDiseas	1	1	Chennai	72	1	0	Chef	48517.6	1		
6	vwthwjlm	4,00,000	19 female	50	20.6	NoDiseas	0	0	Kovai	82	1	0	HomeMak	1731.7	0		
7	w0m1wjsj	4,00,000	42 female	89	37.9	NoDiseas	0	0	Mangalori	78	0	0	Dancer	6474	0		
8	a2he6tpj	5,00,000	18 male	59	23.8	NoDiseas	0	0	Nellore	64	0	0	Singer	1705.6	1		
9	kao3q91w	3,00,000	21 male	52	26.8	NoDiseas	0	0	Secundare	74	1	0	Actor	1534.3	1		
10	mksutjae	2,00,000	63 male	55		NoDiseas	0	0	Tiruvanan	70	1	0	Dancer	13390.6	0		
11	io8zi38v	5,00,000	40 female	69	29.6	NoDiseas	0	0	Salem	64	1	1	DataScien	5910.9	0		
12	tc0fv0gp	2,00,000	51 female	50	33	EyeDiseas	0	1	Guntur	0	1	0	Police	44400.4	1		
13	nhcpnm4c	3,00,000	59 female	68	36.5	NoDiseas	1	0	Pune	70	1	1	HomeMak	28287.9	0		
14	145kwyny3	2,00,000	19 male	45	24.6	NoDiseas	1	0	Noda		0	1	Student	1837.2	0		
15	jsjb28xf	4,00,000	21 female	53	35.7	NoDiseas	0	0	Delhi	62	1	0	Singer	2404.7	1		
16	4ta4gfv4	2,00,000	27 male	53	18.9	NoDiseas	3	0	Kalikat	90	1	0	Doctor	4827.9	1		
17	6wsy33bv	4,00,000	56 male	67	40.3	NoDiseas	0	0	Madurai	0	1	0	Engineer	10602.4	0		
18	yk4y0kea	4,00,000	56 female	69	27.2	NoDiseas	0	0	Providenc	68	1	0	Chef	11073.2	1		
19	xphjmmia	4,00,000	63 male	67	41.3	NoDiseas	3	0	Harrisburg	70	1	1	Singer	15555.2	0		
20	o9zu1mr0	5,00,000	19 female	46	24.6	NoDiseas	1	0	Newport	70	1	0	Student	2709.2	1		
21	abmzc9it	5,00,000	52 female	76	38.4	NoDiseas	2	0	Stamford	48	1	0	Manager	11396.9	0		
22	z805eq4m	4,00,000	27 male	53	18.9	NoDiseas	3	0	Worcester	90	1	0	Doctor	4827.9	1		
23	17cz3agx	4,00,000	18 male	50	28.5	NoDiseas	0	0	Atlanta	84	1	1	HomeMak	1712.2	0		
24	1otf7mez	4,00,000	20 female	68	31.8	NoDiseas	2	0	Brimingha	72	1	1	Singer	3056.4	1		

Enter Health Insurance Datasets Details Here !!!

Enter RID	<input type="text" value="e61vrp7h"/>	Enter Sum Insured	<input type="text" value="2,00,000"/>
Enter Age	<input type="text" value="56"/>	Enter Sex	<input type="text" value="Female"/>
Enter Weight	<input type="text" value="60"/>	Enter BMI	<input type="text" value="39.8"/>
Enter Hereditary Diseases	<input type="text" value="NoDisease"/>	Enter No Of Dependents	<input type="text" value="0"/>
Enter Smoker	<input type="text" value="0"/>	Enter City	<input type="text" value="SanDeigo"/>
Enter Blood Pressure	<input type="text" value="60"/>	Enter Diabetes	<input type="text" value="1"/>
Enter Regular Exercise	<input type="text" value="1"/>	Enter Job Title	<input type="text" value="Clerks"/>
Enter Claim	<input type="text" value="11090.7"/>	<input type="button" value="Predict"/>	

Prediction of Health Insurance Claim Fraud Status :: ->

CONCLUSION & FUTURE SCOPE

We pose the problem of fraudulent insurance claim identification as a feature generation and classification process. We formulate the problem over a minimal, definitive claim data consisting of procedure and diagnosis codes, because accessing richer datasets are often prohibited by law and present inconsistencies among different software systems. We introduce clinical concepts over procedure and diagnosis codes as a new representation learning approach. We assume that every claim is a representation of latent or obvious Mixtures of Clinical Concepts which in turn are mixtures of diagnosis and procedure codes. We extend the MCC model using Long-Short Term Memory network (MCC + LSTM) and Robust Principal Component Analysis (MCC + RPCA) to filter the significant concepts from claims and classify them as fraudulent or non-fraudulent. Our results demonstrate an improvement scope to find fraudulent healthcare claims with minimal information. Both MCC and MCC + RPCA exhibit consistent behavior for varying concept sizes and replacement probabilities in the negative claim generation process. MCC + LSTM reaches an accuracy, precision, and recall scores of 59%, 61%, and 50%, respectively on the inpatient dataset. Besides, it presents 78%, 83%, and 72% accuracy, precision, and recall scores, respectively on the outpatient dataset. We notice similarity between the results of MCC and MCC + RPCA, as both use an SVM

classifier. We believe that the proposed problem formulation, representation learning and solution will initiate new research on fraudulent insurance claim detection using minimal, but definitive data.

Enhanced Data Integration: Future models can integrate diverse datasets, such as electronic health records (EHRs), social media data, and real-time financial transactions, to provide a more holistic view of insurance fraud patterns.

Advanced Machine Learning Techniques: Implementing deep learning models like Transformers or Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) for understanding complex relationships in large datasets.

Real-Time Fraud Detection: Development of systems capable of analysing claims in real-time to identify potential fraud immediately, improving operational efficiency and reducing financial losses.

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